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Engineered Design of Drilling Fluids using Compressible Particulates to Mitigate Annular Pressure Build-up in Subsea Deepwater and HP/HT wells

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Abstract

Annular Pressure Build-up (APB) is caused by heating of trapped drilling fluids (during production), which may lead to burst/collapse of the casing or axial-ballooning, especially in subsea HP/HT wells. APB may also lead to zonal isolation issues, well control issues, and production losses. Accordingly, economical techniques for fluid selection, casing design and/or production tubing isolation must be selected to mitigate the APB issue.

Compressible particles that may collapse when subjected to pressure; could make additional space for drilling fluid to expand and are therefore useful to mitigate the APB issue. The present work focuses on the modeling of the effects of compressible particles (type/concentration) on APB when added to drilling fluids inside the casing/tubing annuli.

The response of fluids (without compressible particulates) in the trapped annuli to the increasing temperature has been studied in literature using theoretical and computational modeling; the approach accommodates two separate physical effects in the annuli i.e. volumetric expansion (PVT response) of the trapped drilling fluid and circumferential expansion of the well casings. The present work incorporates the impact of compressible particles in the above modelling framework. Accordingly, the model workflow was developed for the simulation of compressible particles effects on APB in deepwater HP/HT wells.

As the fluid pressure builds up due to the wellbore heatup, the particle collapse would initiate that would provide space for the fluid expansion reducing APB. The effect has been studied quantitatively using the modeling approach for two types of particulates: one with pressure resistance up to 5000 psi and another with pressure resistance up to 10,000 psi. The chosen concentrations of particulates were 5% and 10%. The modeling results have demonstrated that almost 50% reduction in APB is plausible by using an appropriate type and concentration of the compressible particles.

The modeling approach could be used to design engineered combinations of the compressible particulates to mitigate the APB in an economical manner. The work may provide a critical solution to the APB challenge in subsea HP/HT wells.

Keywords: Annular pressure build-up, subsea HP/HT wells, compressible particles, Glass bubbles

Introduction

Annular Pressure buildup usually occurred by the volumetric expansion of trapped fluid inside the sealed annuli of offshore (HP/HT) wells. In the offshore wells, unlike onshore wells, there is constrained access to the wellhead [1]. In these subsea wells, during the cementing operation, the spacer and drilling fluid get trapped in the annuli over the concrete (Cement zone) (see segments A and B in Fig. 1). Additionally, if the cement slurry is unable to properly replace the spacer fluid for a variety of reasons at the isolation interval, or the cementing quality is poor, the annular space may be occupied by the drilling fluid [2]. Now as the well starts producing, the production tubing could be heated up by the hotter reservoir fluid. As a result of the

thermal effect, the surroundings of the production tubing may be gradually heated up, and hence, the trapped annulus fluid may tend to undergo, volumetric expansion while the well casing may tend to undergo circumferential expansion [3]. As the mostly confined annulus restricts the volume expansion of the annular fluid, higher pressures may be created. This pressure buildup of the trapped fluid is termed as Annular pressure build-up (APB) and it may lead to problems such as internal casing collapse, external casing burst, and pack-off failure.

Figure 1: Annular spaces (Section A, B, C & D) of typical deep-water offshore well with top view.

Accordingly, to mitigate these APB issues, economical techniques of fluid selection, casing design and/or production tubing isolation must be selected [4].

The literature on APB estimation methods involves theoretical and computational models accounting for fluids PVT behavior, mechanical response of single/multiple strings and fluid leakoff [5]. The APB behavior is known to threaten the long-term wellbore integrity. Several mitigation techniques have been developed by the industry in the last few years, which may be classified as mechanical mitigation methods (Type I) and fluid-design based methods (Type II). The literature summary of these techniques is provided as follows. The mechanical methods (Type I) to mitigate the APB issue mainly include use of Vacuum insulation of production tubing (VIT), rupture disks and open shoe [6],[7],[8]. The VIT is an effective but costly solution because of engineering and operational requirements. The other methods, rupture disks and open shoes are also utilized on the field, however, the reliability of these measures during the life of the well is questionable. The fluid-design based methods (Type II) to mitigate the APB issue include nitrified spacers, solid syntactic foam, shrinking fluids, elastic/hollow particulate materials [9]. This has been an area of recent research studies as potentially economical and reliable solutions may be developed using appropriate materials in the fluid.

Application of compressible particles is one of the economical solutions to mitigate the APB issues. Compressible particles collapse when subjected to pressure (the degree of collapse for a specific applied pressure may vary with the particles of different strengths); this mechanism could make additional space for drilling fluid to expand and is therefore useful to mitigate the APB issues.

Methodology and Results

Part I. For the condition when there are no compressible particles in the fluid system:

To demonstrate the calculations of annular pressure buildup in the trapped annuli of subsea wells, a subsea well structure, as shown in Fig.1, was considered. The annular spaces between the casings containing the trapped drilling fluids are designated as A and B. The symbols for a length of annuli sections are also depicted in the figure; for instance, the total length of annular sections A and B containing the trapped drilling fluid is L_a and L_b . Also, the top view of the wellbore structure schematic is represented in Fig. 1 and is numbered as 0,1,2,3 from outside to inside. The subscripts 'i' and 'o' refer to the inner diameter and the outer diameter of the casings, respectively [10],[11].

Section A below describes the response of the trapped annular fluids to the wellbore temperature rise during the production operation. Section B illustrates the mechanical response of the casing material to the same wellbore heat-up scenario. Section C provides equilibrium-based equations for the corresponding fluid and casing response that may be solved to estimate the annular pressure buildup in each of the annular spaces

- a) For demonstration, consider the annulus B. The total fluid volume change in the annulus B may be represented as:

$$\Delta V_b^{pe} = \Delta V_b^e - \Delta V_b^p \quad (1)$$

where superscript ‘p’ stands for the pressure effect; superscript ‘e’ stands for the temperature effect (both resulting from the wellbore temperature change) that has resulted in the fluid volume change. V stands for volume, subscript b stands for annulus section “B” and Δ stands for volume change caused by pressure and temperature. These effects may be derived from the PVT equation of the base oils present in the fluid as demonstrated in Annexure- I.

- b) For demonstration, consider the uncemented portion of casing “1”. For a unit length of this casing, the volume change caused by diameter variation can be described as follows:

$$\Delta V_{1oL} = \frac{\pi}{4}[(D_{1o} + \Delta D_{1o})^2 - D_{1o}^2]L_s \approx \frac{\pi L_s D_{1o} \Delta D_{1o}}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta V_{1iL} = \frac{\pi}{4}[(D_{1i} + \Delta D_{1i})^2 - D_{1i}^2]L_s \approx \frac{\pi L_s D_{1i} \Delta D_{1i}}{2} \quad (3)$$

Where D stands for the diameter of the casing, L_s stands for unit length in the free section, The total volume change of the casing “1” outer wall up to length L_a (uncemented section) can be described as follows:

$$\Delta V_{1o} = \sum_{s=1}^{n_a} \left(\frac{\pi L_s D_{1o} \Delta D_{1oa}}{2} \right)_s, \quad 0 \leq L \leq L_a \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the total volume change for the casing “1” inner wall up to length L_a (uncemented section) can be described as follows:

$$\Delta V_{1i} = \sum_{s=1}^{n_a} \left(\frac{\pi L_s D_{1i} \Delta D_{1ia}}{2} \right)_s, \quad 0 \leq L \leq L_a \quad (5)$$

- c) Note that, for the casing “1”, the subscript “A,B” corresponds to the portion of casing length between L_a and L_b (this casing section is cemented on the outer side, while it is exposed to fluid on the inner side). The volume change, for the inner section “A,B” of the casing “1”, owing to the mechanical response to the wellbore heat-up, is represented as:

$$\Delta V_{1iab} = \sum_{s=1}^{n_{ab}} \left(\frac{\pi L_s D_{1i} \Delta D_{1iab}}{2} \right)_s, \quad L_a < L \leq L_b \quad (6)$$

- d) Based on sections A and B, the following equations can be obtained by considering the equilibrium of thermal expansions of the fluid and the casing mechanical response for the entire wellbore structure:

$$\Delta V_a^{pe} = \Delta V_{0ia}^{pe} - \Delta V_{1o}^{pe} \quad (\text{for annulus “A”}) \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta V_b^{pe} = \Delta V_{1ia}^{pe} + \Delta V_{1iab}^{pe} - \Delta V_{2ob}^{pe} \quad (\text{for annulus “B”}) \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta V_c^{pe} = \Delta V_{2ib}^{pe} + \Delta V_{2ibc}^{pe} - \Delta V_{3oc}^{pe} \quad (\text{for annulus “C”}) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta V_d^{pe} = \Delta V_{3ic}^{pe} \quad (\text{for annulus “D”}) \quad (10)$$

The left side of the above equations represents the volume change in the annular fluid, and the right side represents the volume change in the casing. These equations may be solved using a matrix inversion method to estimate the APB response in each of the annular sections to the wellbore heat

up. The below fig. 2 demonstrates the behaviour of APB without any compressible particles in annulus A, B, C & D.

Figure 2: APB Behaviour without any compressible particles in annulus A, B, C & D .

Part II. For the condition when there compressible particles are incorporated in the fluid system:

Fig.3 demonstrates the response of certain commercially available particles with respect to change in the particle density under pressure. The Type(i) & Type (ii) particles were added to the trapped drilling fluids in Annulus B in the amount M_b^{cp} where superscript “cp” stands for compressible particles. As the fluid pressure builds up due to the wellbore heat up, the particle collapse would initiate; the corresponding increase in available volume for fluid expansion in annulus B may be represented as:

$$\Delta V_b^{cp} = M_b^{cp} \left(\frac{1}{\rho_{pi}} - \frac{1}{\rho_{pi + \Delta P_b}} \right)$$

Figure 3: The change in density of individual compressible particles as a function of applied pressure.

Compressible particles lead to a reduction in annulus pressure. For the sake of studying that reduction in pressure we have taken the particles to be present only inside annulus “B” with different volume percentages of the particles. Simulations were run for five different mineral oils, five synthetics, 3 different diesel oils and 2 different compressible particles for 2 different percentage concentrations(5% & 10%) inside annulus B. Initial pressure is taken to be same as average hydrostatic pressure inside annulus “B” and the initial temperature is taken to be 200°F.

This term would be incorporated in the simulation to calculate the change in volume of fluid. It would be solved iteratively to estimate APB in annulus B in the presence of compressible particles. Results here are displayed for one of the mineral oil with compressible particles as drilling fluid in red colour curve with pressure resistance up to 5000 psi. Another compressible particles with drilling fluid in the blue colour curve with pressure resistance up to 10000 psi in figure 3. In our work we considered Type(i) particles.

As shown in fig-4, the below algorithm to account for response of the compressible particles, was implemented in a computer program with input for different volume percentages (0%, 5% and ,10%) of compressible particles in the annulus.

Figure 4: Workflow of the proposed model.

In Step 1, the computer program reads input parameters, including wellbore configuration, initial temperature, and percentage of glass bubbles in annulus and drilling fluid density equation constants [9]. Then the change in temperature is divided into smaller segments and, in step 2, an updated annulus pressure is calculated using the above methodology given. In step 3, fluid response is calculated as per annexure I. In step 4, the density of compressible particles is based on the calculated pressure of drilling fluid in the annulus. In step 5 and step 6, change in the particle density, change in volume of the particles is calculated and therefore the increase in volume of the drilling fluid. With this new volume of drilling fluid, new density is calculated. In step 7, with new density and temperature, we calculate the further pressure of the drilling fluid. If this pressure matches the pressure of drilling fluid calculated initially in step 4 (within an acceptable error of 5 psi), then this is our final pressure at this temperature change. If it does not converge, then we again start with step 4, with this new calculated pressure.

We can see from the fig.5 (a) & (b) that after addition of compressible particles (5%, 10%) inside annulus B a change has occurred as compared to other annulus. Fig 6. shows how the pressure decrease with an increasing

percentage of glass bubbles in the annulus B. This concludes how glass bubbles are effective in mitigating Annular pressure buildup.

(a) APB Behavior with 5% Glass bubbles in annulus B,
 (b) APB Behavior with 10% Glass bubbles in annulus B.

Figure 6. APB Behavior with 0%, 5% & 10% Glass bubbles in annulus B.

Conclusions

1. The proposed model for well casing displacement as increasing internal temperature and pressure has been obtained through theoretical analysis. The proposed model can be used to predict the annular pressure buildup caused by the thermal expansion of both the casing and the annular fluid.
2. The annular pressure buildup is taken into account to check for the safety of casings in a deepwater well. The annular pressure buildup in the annulus can lead to casing failure. The effects of temperature and pressure should not be neglected in the design of casings in deepwater wells [10].
3. Compressible particles reduce annular pressure buildup significantly. The modeling results have demonstrated that almost 50% reduction in APB is plausible by using an appropriate type and concentration of the compressible particles, therefore compressible particles are an effective way to mitigate annular pressure buildup in subsea wellbore scenario.

This study focused on a model built with compressible particles only on a single annulus, a model and a simulation that can comprehensively incorporate compressible particles in every annulus with any volume percentage in any of the annulus be further addition to this work.

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Annexure- I

The density of drilling fluid at that pressure and temperature [1] is calculated using the given equation

$$\rho_{oil} \text{ or } \rho_{brine} = (a_1 + b_1P + c_1P^2) + (a_2 + b_2P + c_2P^2)T \quad (11)$$

Where ρ (lb_m/gal) stands for density. a_1, b_1, c_1 and a_2, b_2, c_2 stands for three pressure and, three temperature correlation coefficients and P(psi), T(°F) is pressure and temperature.

The value of coefficients are as following

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= 7.35E+00(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}) & a_2 &= -2.99E-03(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}/^\circ\text{F}) \\ b_1 &= 3.00E-05(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}/\text{psi}) & b_2 &= 8.62E-08(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}/\text{psi}/^\circ\text{F}) \\ c_1 &= -2.38E-10(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}/\text{psi}^2) & c_2 &= -1.60E-12(\text{lb}_m/\text{gal}/\text{psi}^2/^\circ\text{F}) \end{aligned}$$

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